

Evaluation of the ECCO-Darwin Ocean Biogeochemistry State Estimate vs. In-situ Observations

Dustin Carroll^{1,2}, Dimitris Menemenlis², Hong Zhang², Matt Mazloff³, Galen McKinley⁴,
Amanda Fay⁴, Stephanie Dutkiewicz⁵, Jonathan Lauderdale⁵, Ian Fenty²,
and ECCO consortium members

¹Moss Landing Marine Laboratories, San José State University

²Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology

³Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego

⁴Columbia University and Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory

⁵Massachusetts Institute of Technology

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Summary

This document provides 1) a brief introduction to ECCO-Darwin v05 and 2) evaluation of the model against a suite of *in-situ* ocean observations. ECCO-Darwin is an ongoing global-ocean biogeochemistry state estimate in the framework of Carroll et al. (2020).

ECCO-Darwin model output is available at the ECCO Data Portal and ECCO Drive:

https://data.nas.nasa.gov/ecco/data.php?dir=/eccodata/llc_270/ecco_darwin_v5/
https://ecco.jpl.nasa.gov/drive/files/ECCO2/LLC270/ECCO-Darwin_extension

The ECCO Data Portal is used to host input and output files for published solutions, while ECCO Drive is used to host the latest time extensions of the model.

Each user must first register for a NASA Earthdata account at

<https://urs.earthdata.nasa.gov/users/new> in order to access the files in ECCO Drive.

Model code and platform-independent instructions for running ECCO-Darwin simulations are available at: https://github.com/MITgcm-contrib/ecco_darwin

Fork of MITgcm with Darwin ecosystem model added is available at:

<https://github.com/darwinproject/darwin3>

Darwin package documentation is available at:

https://darwin3.readthedocs.io/en/latest/phys_pkgs/darwin.html

Code for generating the figures shown this document is available at:

https://github.com/MITgcm-contrib/ecco_darwin/tree/master/code_util/evaluation/

1. Period of analysis

The latest v05 ECCO-Darwin solution spans January 1992 to December 2022. Future extensions covering 1992 to near-present are planned on a semi-annual basis.

2. Model configuration

A detailed description of the ECCO-Darwin model setup, observational constraints, and optimization methodology is presented in Carroll et al. (2020). The latest ECCO-Darwin solution (v05) is based on ocean circulation and physical tracers (i.e., temperature, salinity, and sea ice) from the Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the Ocean (ECCO) LLC270 global-ocean and sea-ice data synthesis (Zhang et al., 2018).

The “Lat-Lon-Cap” (LLC) grid topology is described in Forget et al. (2015). Horizontal grid spacing varies spatially from 12 km at high latitudes to 28 km at mid-latitudes. The vertical grid spacing increases from 10 m near the surface to 457 m near the deepest ocean seafloor. The model resolution is too coarse to properly resolve mesoscale eddies. To account for resolved tracer mixing associated with unresolved mesoscale eddies, the model employs the Redi (1982) and Gent and McWilliams (1990) schemes. Vertical mixing is parameterized with a combination of the Gaspar et al. (1990) scheme and a constant background diffusivity.

The LLC270 ocean state estimate is used at each time step (1200 s) to drive an online biogeochemistry and ecosystem model provided by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology Darwin Project (Dutkiewicz et al., 2015, 2020; Follows et al., 2007); taken together these components form ECCO-Darwin. The Darwin model includes the cycling of carbon, phosphorus (PO_4), iron (Fe), silica (SiO_2), oxygen (O_2), and alkalinity. Matter is cycled from inorganic nutrients, through living and dead organic matter, and remineralized back to inorganic forms. All particulates are instantly removed once they reach the seafloor as a crude parameterization of sedimentation and to prevent model instability due to the accumulation of particulates at the bottom. Nitrogen cycling explicitly includes nitrate (NO_3), nitrite (NO_2), and ammonium pools (NH_4). Carbonate chemistry is based on the efficient solver of Follows et al. (2006). Air-sea CO_2 flux is computed using the parameterization of Wanninkhof (1992) and forced with apCO_2 from the zonally-averaged National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Marine Boundary Layer Reference (NOAA MBL) product (Andrews et al., 2014). Atmospheric iron dust deposition at the ocean surface and terrestrial runoff along coastal boundaries is forced using the monthly climatology of Mahowald et al. (2009) and Fekete et al. (2002), respectively. Terrestrial runoff consists of freshwater only and does not include nutrients nor carbon.

The Darwin ecology includes five large-to-small phytoplankton functional types (diatoms, other large eukaryotes, *Synechococcus*, and low- and high-light adapted *Prochlorococcus*), along with two zooplankton types that graze preferentially on either large eukaryotes or small picoplankton. Biogeochemical properties (i.e., inorganic carbon and nutrients, phytoplankton and zooplankton, dissolved organic matter, and detrital particles) are treated as prognostic variables and are advected and mixed by the LLC270 ocean circulation.

3. Observational constraints and data assimilation

Physical observations are assimilated using the adjoint method (i.e., 4-D-Var; Wunsch et al., 2009; Wunsch and Heimbach, 2013), which minimizes a weighted least squares sum of model-data misfit (the cost function) to optimize initial conditions, time-varying surface-ocean boundary conditions, and time-invariant, three-dimensional mixing coefficients for along-isopycnal, cross-isopycnal, and isopycnal thickness diffusivity. Because the initial conditions, surface boundary conditions, and mixing coefficients are estimated as part of the adjoint-method optimization, the ECCO LLC270 ocean circulation estimate has negligible drift.

The biogeochemical initial conditions and model parameters are optimized using a low-dimensional Green's Functions approach (Menemenlis et al., 2005) after the optimization of the physical model. The mixing coefficients from the adjoint optimization are applied to both the physical and biogeochemical fields. The biogeochemical observations used to evaluate and adjust ECCO-Darwin include: (1) surface ocean fugacity ($f\text{CO}_2$) from the monthly-gridded Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas (SOCATv5 2023, Bakker et al., 2016), (2) GLODAP ship-based profiles of NO_3 , PO_4 , SiO_2 , O_2 , Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), and alkalinity (Key et al., 2015; Olsen et al., 2016), and (3) BGC-Argo float profiles of NO_3 and O_2 (Riser et al., 2016; Riser et al., 2018).

What sets the ECCO LLC270 and ECCO-Darwin solutions apart from conventional discrete or gridded observational products, is that, in addition to good agreement with observational data, ECCO products provide a complete suite of ocean and sea ice variables that describe the entire physical and biogeochemical state of the ocean and sea ice (such as 3-D temperature, salinity, and carbon, 3-D velocity, sea level, bottom pressure). Furthermore, in contrast to most other ocean reanalyses, the ECCO product fields, by design, are physically consistent with each other and with the air-sea fluxes, allowing for a full physical accounting of their temporal evolution, fundamental to studies of attribution and causation. For a description of ECCO-Darwin biogeochemical budgets and analysis, see Carroll et al. (2022).

4. Model-data evaluation

In the accompanying figures, we compare monthly-mean ECCO-Darwin values vs. *in-situ* observations in 1) the global ocean at various depth levels and 2) spatially-averaged in the open-ocean biomes from Fay and McKinley (2014) and 5 superbiomes defined in Carroll et al. (2020). Observations include SOCATv2023 (Bakker et al., 2023), GLODAPv2.2023 (Lauvset et al. 2024), and BGC-Argo (M. Mazloff, pers. comm.) data. Monthly-mean model values are paired with closest space-time-located (x,y,z,t) *in-situ* data. All map plots show values at model grid cell locations. All values shown in individual superbiomes/biomes represent area-weighted and volume-weighted means for surface ocean and depth-range analysis, respectively; vertical profiles represent area-weighted means at each vertical level. To avoid spin-up drift, all maps, scatter plots, vertical profiles, and seasonal climatology plots start in January 1995. All time-series plots begin in January 1992 (instead of January 1995) to show the complete model spin-up period (when observations are available).

5. Description of figures

The table below shows a list and description of all figures. The leftmost column color provides a quick index for the type of observation (orange = SOCAT, blue = GLODAP, and gray = BGC-Argo).

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	162–164	ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo time series	All data from 1992–2022, 0 to 100-m depth	Blue and grey circles show all data and model values, respectively; blue and red lines show annual-mean data and model values, respectively
	166–168	ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo time series	All data from 1992–2022, 100 to 500-m depth	Blue and grey circles show all data and model values, respectively; blue and red lines show annual-mean data and model values, respectively
	170–172	ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo time series	All data from 1992–2022, 500 to 6000-m depth	Blue and grey circles show all data and model values, respectively; blue and red lines show annual-mean data and model values, respectively

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Superbiome and biome regions

Superbiomes

Biomes

ECCO-Darwin vs. SOCAT model-data difference map: surface ocean

Surface-ocean fCO₂

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP model-data difference map: 0 to 100-m depth

Pot. Temp., 0 to 100-m Depth

Salinity, 0 to 100-m Depth

DIC, 0 to 100-m Depth

Alkalinity, 0 to 100-m Depth

pH, 0 to 100-m Depth

NO₃, 0 to 100-m Depth

PO₄, 0 to 100-m Depth

SiO₂, 0 to 100-m Depth

O₂, 0 to 100-m Depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP model-data difference map: 100 to 500-m depth

Pot. Temp., 100 to 500-m Depth

Salinity, 100 to 500-m Depth

DIC, 100 to 500-m Depth

Alkalinity, 100 to 500-m Depth

pH, 100 to 500-m Depth

NO₃, 100 to 500-m Depth

PO₄, 100 to 500-m Depth

SiO₂, 100 to 500-m Depth

O₂, 100 to 500-m Depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP model-data difference map: 500 to 6000-m depth

Pot. Temp., 500 to 6000-m Depth

Salinity, 500 to 6000-m Depth

DIC, 500 to 6000-m Depth

Alkalinity, 500 to 6000-m Depth

pH, 500 to 600-m Depth

NO₃, 500 to 6000-m Depth

PO₄, 500 to 6000-m Depth

SiO₂, 500 to 6000-m Depth

O₂, 500 to 6000-m Depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo model-data difference map: 0 to 100-m depth

pH, 0 to 100-m Depth

NO₃, 0 to 100-m Depth

O₂, 0 to 100-m Depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo model-data difference map: 100 to 500-m depth

pH, 100 to 500-m Depth

NO₃, 100 to 500-m Depth

O₂, 100 to 500-m Depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo model-data difference map: 500 to 6000-m depth

pH, 500 to 6000-m Depth

NO₃, 500 to 6000-m Depth

O₂, 500 to 6000-m Depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. SOCAT scatter: surface ocean

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP scatter: all depths

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo scatter: all depths

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP vertical profiles: all depths

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo vertical profiles: all depths

ECCO-Darwin vs. SOCAT seasonal climatology: surface ocean

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP seasonal climatology: 0 to 100-m depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP seasonal climatology: 100 to 500-m depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. GLODAP seasonal climatology: 500 to 6000-m depth

Figure showing monthly salinity (psu) for various biomes (NH, NS, EQ, SS, SH, NP1, NP2, NP3, NP4, WPE, EPE, SP, NA1, NA2, NA3, NA4, AE, SA, IO, SO1, SO2, SO3, All Biomes, Global) comparing observed data (Obs., blue dashed line) and model results (Model, red solid line). The x-axis represents the month (1-12) and the y-axis represents salinity in psu. The legend indicates that blue dashed lines represent observed data and red solid lines represent model results.

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo seasonal climatology: 0 to 100-m depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo seasonal climatology: 100 to 500-m depth

ECCO-Darwin vs. BGC-Argo seasonal climatology: 500 to 6000-m depth

SOCAT time series: surface ocean

GLODAP time series: 0 to 100-m depth

GLODAP time series: 100 to 500-m depth

GLODAP time series: 500 to 6000-m depth

BGC-Argo time series: 0 to 100-m depth

BGC-Argo time series: 100 to 500-m depth

BGC-Argo time series: 500 to 6000-m depth

